

The Effect of Online Classes on Students Performance During the Outbreak of the COVID-19 Virus “A Case Study at The University of Halabja in Northern Iraq”

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to identify the factors that influence student performance in relation to online classes during the COVID-19 pandemic period and to establish the relationship between these variables. The study is of a quantitative nature, and data was collected from 350 people from all disciplines who were studying at Halabja University in northern Iraq through an online survey. Correlation design was used to test the relationships between attributes of dependent and independent variables using Pearson's Product Moment Co-effective correlation (r). The results showed that four independent factors were used in the study. Instructor quality, course design, quick feedback and student expectation positively impact student performance. The factors are essential to obtain a high level of performance for our online customers. This study is being conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic period to investigate the impact of online teaching on student performance.

Keywords: COVID-19, Quality of instructor, Course design, Instructor's prompt feedback, Expectations, Perceived performance.

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INTRODUCTION

Learning refers to the systematic acquisition of new preferences, attitudes, values, skills, behavior, knowledge, and understanding in schools and universities. For a long period, approaches such as research, assignments, videos, storytelling, training, and discussion have been used to help learners acquire knowledge and values (Altun, 2017). The learning, or education, might be achieved through self-study where an individual learns everything by themselves or with little guidance, or they could attend classes-which could be virtual or face-to-face. In Kurdistan, attending classes is more advocated especially for the K-12 students who have not yet mastered the art of self-study and need immense guidance to learn new concepts. However, universities and colleges have adopted virtual learning, more so those who are

working and learning at the same time. The choice of a learning style is all dependent on the academic environment, the capacity of student's learning, and their level (Pham, L., Limbu, Y. B., Bui, T. K., Nguyen, H. T., & Pham, H. T. 2019).

The whole orientation of education, both online and in-class was disrupted in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. The Covonavirus disease (COVID-19) has had devastating effects on all sectors of the global economy since the World Health Organization (WHO) announced it as a pandemic in March 2020. The first case in Kurdistan was reported on 1st March 2020. A rise in the number of confirmed cases and deaths forced the government to instill more stringent regulations across the region to ensure safety of its people. The Kurdistan Regional Government (KRG), like other governments around the world, closed all the schools as a preventive measure to stop the spread of the COVID-19. The closure affected about 1.7 million students in about 6,800 public schools (UNICEF, 2020). The number includes refugees in camps whose conditions before then were already dire. Up on this closure, the government facilitated online learning by introducing televised education because over half of the families in the region did not have access to the internet (UNICEF, 2020). The government closed primary schools, universities, and colleges which had a massive negative impact on education because social distance was an important element in preventing the spread of the disease. Education agencies, governmental and non-governmental, local, and international, tried to devise alternative approaches to settling the dilemma. However, there was no other alternative other than introduce distance learning where students were supposed to access education from home through the internet to ensure minimal to interruption to the teaching-learning process in all schools. Multiple entities took part in this transition to ensure that the students receive quality online educational materials and perform their evaluations without a glitch. While many schools were able to adapt to this situation, others had a challenge of internet access because over 54% of families in the region did not have access to internet (UNICEF, 2020). The education ministry in the region was keen on the fact that not all children could access the internet, and this would lead to disparities in the teaching-learning process. Many families and communities in Kurdistan have no access to computers, internet connection, and smartphones. Besides, there is a culture that prevented female students from having access to the internet for learning purposes. Despite these challenges, the government still looked for ways to keep students learning through new technologies. The crisis forced organizations that were previously hesitant to accept new technologies do so to facilitate the learning process. This proved to be a difficult time for the education sectors to achieve their objectives during this trying period. The effects varied across different schools, areas, and particular courses; for instance, medical education was among the most affected.

Online education meant carrying out the pedagogical processes using electronic devices that students could access such as smartphones, laptops, and computers. According to (Singh, V., & Thurman, A. 2019), virtual education through the internet makes a platform which eases the education process by making it more flexible, creative, and student-centered. It can increase equality by making education accessible to everyone with an internet connection and is cost-effective more so for the students in remote and rural areas. Therefore, education provision especially in poor countries becomes easier with WHO identifying it as a crucial instrument to meet educational needs across the world (Colace, F., De Santo, M., & Pietrosanto, A. 2006). Following the closure of schools, colleges and universities implemented several creative approaches as a way of combating the crisis in the region by applications and software such as Microsoft Teams, Zoom, and Google Classroom to help students take online classes. Home-

based learning was accepted as the new norm across the region, helping to boost learners' confidence and certainty and to help the schools to keep in touch with the students throughout the period as everyone fought to adapt to the new conditions (Agnolotto, R., & Queiroz, V. 2020).

Through this adoption and adaptation to the new pedagogical paradigms, the education sector in Kurdistan had no option than to leverage assets available to them to facilitate virtual learning as people stayed and worked from home. This was the best alternative available rather than trying to recreate schools to cater for the government's social distancing requirements. This system has both merits and demerits for all the stakeholders in the education sector. On one hand, the process could bring private meaningful learning experience to learners to connect them to home environment and maintain their local identities while using the devices at their disposal. As (Perienen, A. 2020) assert, adjustments were inevitable for both teachers, institutions and students. This is true as virtually all institutions of higher learning, especially universities, had to redraft the extant policies to integrate virtual learning pedagogy as an emergency approach following the uncertainty of the situation at hand.

The COVID-19 pandemic has introduced a demand for online education in a way that Kurdish higher education institutions cannot keep up. If such a demand exists, a sudden relocation may be impossible, especially in areas where the required resources are not readily available. The teachers were not well versed in the art of distance learning and making sure the syllabus was completed on time. Administrators may also need extensive training on how to manage teams remotely and get all tasks done on time. Finally, student resistance can hamper any implementations by the government of integrating virtual learning methods in place. With such difficulty posed by the epidemic in the region and beyond, and the potential impacts that can be experienced from future epidemics, it is clear that Kurdistan's ability to quickly utilize available technology and mobilize stakeholders to devise relevant emergency mechanisms to adapt to any new. The introduction of relevant infrastructure modifications will determine the continuity of learning in all universities. The effects of COVID-19 on the education sector have been felt in all countries globally, including Iraq and Kurdistan. The reason is that there was a sudden disruption in pedagogical processes in all educational institutions, both from kindergarten to twelfth grade and in higher education institutions alike.

The disparity in home-based learning poses a huge problem to the acquisition of online learning programs. The inequality is majorly presented by a difference in the socio-economic aspects of the Kurdistan community which have been a major issue for a long time. The socioeconomic status of a family affected how well a student received online classes. Those living in impoverished conditions do not have the relevant resources, locking them out from accessing the learning materials shared remotely. This explains the resistance that the online learning adoption faced from parents whose students studied in public schools as their situations are already dire.

According to (Ali, B. J., Gardi, B., Jabbar Othman, B., Burhan Ismael, N., Sorguli, S., Sabir, B. Y., & Anwar, G. 2021), a student or parent's choice of university in Kurdistan is greatly influenced by their socioeconomic status. Therefore, those in poor conditions have limited abilities to navigate the disrupted educational landscape in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. There are many aspects that characterize public and private institutions in Kurdistan including funding, infrastructure, teacher-student ratio, and the nature of students enrolled in the university (Qasim, A. M., Al-Askari, P. S. M., Massoud, H. K., & Ayoubi, R. M. 2021). In general, these differences indicate that the public for college students is disadvantaged than

their college peers in private institutions. In fact, even in areas where virtual learning opportunities may be available, the poor infrastructure of the university cannot allow institutions to complete their curricula on time and thus this directly affects the performance of students through course design, instructor quality, Instructor's Prompt Feedback and finally Student expectations.

The adoption of all other teaching methods such as educational technology through course design, instructor quality and student performance only exacerbate the disparities that already exist in the education sector. Inequality in access to education jeopardizes students' earning capacity later in life and threatens to harm students' performance during school. Therefore, the pandemic has only served to increase the educational disparities that already exist in the region. Many researchers have attempted to cover critical issues affecting the successful implementation of e-learning strategies in developed, developing and underdeveloped countries. Many studies have also been conducted on the challenges brought about by the sudden implementation of e-learning in the wake of COVID-19. While the discussion on the various aspects of integrating online learning remains inconclusive, there is no research done on success stories in Kurdistan regarding the challenges faced by various stakeholders while implementing Information and Communication Technology (ICT) despite the potential and promise it has in the sector. education.

The only information available is about news articles and articles from other countries, especially the developed world. News is not scientific and therefore may not be used as a source of information. On the other hand, literature from Western countries cannot be used because the technological environment and socio-economic factors in the West and Iraq are very different. Some of the problems encountered in Iraq such as unreliable power supply, slow development of telecommunications infrastructure, low bandwidth, may not be experienced in other countries, while they may be severe in others. Thus, a successful transition from traditional methods of learning to a technology-based education system needs documented scientific evidence from research such as the current research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The University of Halabja is one of the Iraqi Kurdistan public universities founded in 2011 in the city of Halabja, Halabja Governorate. The university consists of six colleges such as (Science, Human sciences, Basic Education, Physical Education and Sport Sciences, Law and Administration, Education of Sharazoor, and Department of Engineering) (University of Halabja, 2022). Programs last for four years, and students receive BA degrees in their corresponding fields at the end of the fourth year. It has two campuses; the main campus is situated in Halabja, and the secondary is in Sharazoor District. The current president of Halabja University is Prof.Dr. Mahabad Kamil Abdullah (University of Halabja, 2022). Before 2010, Halabja had a college "College of Basic Education" which was part and affiliated with the University of Sulaymaniyah. Then on July 8, 2010, during the Council of Ministers of the Kurdistan Regional Government, the Council of Ministers of the Kurdistan Regional Government issued Resolution No. 1670 declaring the University of Halabja, thus, the College of Basic Education left Sulaymaniyah University and became part of Halabja University. In February 2011 the presidency of Halabja University began its work (University of Halabja, 2022). The University of Halabja has two campuses; the major campus is located at the edge

of the city of Halabja close to Ababaile village. It is a large one and is where all the departments are situated. The other and subsidiary campus is in Sharazoor District containing the college of Education of Sharazoor only (University of Halabja, 2022). University of Halabja is one of the four Iraqi Kurdistan public university partners of the European Union Erasmus Mundus MARHABA Program, the others being Koya, Sulaimani, and Raparin universities. The objective of MARHABA project directly corresponds to the development of further collaboration among EU and Asian Institutions for sending and hosting mobility of talented students and staff, enhancement capacity, transparency, and employability as well as skills and qualification of institutions and individuals (University of Halabja, 2022).

COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND HIGHER EDUCATION

The current pandemic caused by the novel coronavirus (COVID-19) has had a profound impact on our daily activities and has presented us with unprecedented challenges. As the dreadfulness of COVID-19 became crystal clear, globally, governments closed schools to curb the spread of the virus impacting over 90% of the world's enrolled learners (Riggall, 2020; UNESCO, 2020). The intermissions to education can have long-term repercussions, exclusively, for the most vulnerable. This may not only cause loss of short-term learning but also further loss in human capital and diminished economic opportunities in the long-term as well as prejudice towards groups (Watson, 2020; World Bank, 2020a). The COVID-19 outbreak is affecting education in terms of reduction in utilization of schools, lack of quality appropriate education, reduction in access to education services, reduction in availability of education services, lack of maintenance of schools, lack of teacher training, fear of school return and emotional stress caused by outbreak, reduced financial resources, diversion of resources and teachers, confusion and stress for teachers, lack of at-home educational materials, challenges measuring and validating learning, parents unprepared for distance and home schooling, challenges creating, maintaining, improving distance learning, loss of quality teaching and learning, social isolation, emotional disequilibrium and school drop outs (Bozkurt & Sharma, 2020; Hallgarten, 2020; UNESCO, 2020b).

Due to these effects, governments are taking measures to ensure that education continues via emergency remote learning/teaching approaches with many deploying online learning solutions (David et al., 2020; Jalli, 2020; UNESCO, 2020c; 2020d). This may seem experimental to some higher education institutions, typically, those in developing countries like Ghana, and however, there might be others who have managed online teaching/ learning before. Regarding this, several organizations are helping ensure that learners continue their education worldwide. For example, the World Bank is vigorously working with Ministries of Education in numerous countries to support their efforts to employ instructional technologies of all sorts to provide remote learning opportunities for students while schools are closed because of the COVID-19 crisis (World Bank, 2020a). Similarly, UNESCO is helping countries in their labours to alleviate the instantaneous effect of school closures, particularly for more vulnerable and disadvantaged communities, and to facilitate the continuity of education for all through remote learning (UNESCO, 2020a).

However, it seems that higher educational institutions understand the pedagogical, logistical, and technological challenges to these timely measures. Most of the higher educational institutions in low- and middle-income countries, including students and teachers, lacked access to high-speed broadband or digital devices needed to fully deploy online learning options. Thus, transition from in-person to person instruction to emergency remote

learning/online learning has wide-open cavernous digital divides between and within schools and countries (World Bank, 2020a; 2020c), particularly, among low-medium income countries like Ghana. The condition is far poorer for lower resource environments in middle- and- low-income countries with internet dissemination rates typically less than 50% and a large fraction of students without devices to enable emergency remote learning at home (World Bank, 2020c). This result indicates the capacity of parents and even schools to support emergency remote learning or online learning during school closures as result of COVID-19. Per this, higher education institutions need to cogitate substitute ways for students to continue learning when they are not in school, like in the current COVID-19 crisis.

On this account, UNESCO is centering on solidifying capacities of distance learning systems to overcome the digital divide through resources providing support to teachers, parents and caregivers. In equivalent, the Organization is firming its assistance with the open educational resource (OER) community to support openly licensed teaching and learning materials in the framework of the 2019 UNESCO OER Recommendation; identify MOOCs and OERs which can provide online courses and self-directed learning content through both mobile and desktop platforms; support, through the OER4Covid initiative, transition to online learning using OER during the COVID-19 pandemic (UNESCO, 2020f; 2020g).

QUALITY OF INSTRUCTOR

Instructor Quality plays an essential role in affecting the students' satisfaction in online classes. Instructor quality refers to a professional who understands the students' educational needs, has unique teaching skills, and understands how to meet the students' learning needs (Luekens et al., 2004). Marsh (1987) developed five instruments for measuring the instructor's quality, in which the main method was Students' Evaluation of Educational Quality (SEEQ), which delineated the instructor's quality. SEEQ is considered one of the methods most used and embraced unanimously (Grammatikopoulos et al., 2014). SEEQ was a very useful method of feedback by students to measure the instructor's quality (Marsh, 1987). Quality of instructor with high fanaticism on student's learning has a positive impact on their Performance. Quality of instructor is one of the most critical measures for student Performance, leading to the education process's outcome (Munteanu et al., 2010). Suppose the teacher delivers the course effectively and influence the students to do better in their studies. In that case, this process leads to student Performance and enhances the learning process (Ladyshevsky, 2013). Furthermore, understanding the need of learner by the instructor also ensures student Performance (Kauffman, 2015). Hence the hypothesis that the quality of instructor significantly affects the Performance of the students was included in this study.

H1: The quality of the instructor positively affects the Performance of the students.

COURSE DESIGN

The Course Design refers to curriculum knowledge, program organization, instructional goals, and course structure (Wright, 2003). If well planned, course design increasing the satisfaction of pupils with the system (Almaiah & Alyoussef, 2019). Mtebe and Raisamo (2014) proposed that effective course design will help in improving the performance through learners' knowledge and skills (Khan & Yildiz, 2020). However, if the course is not designed effectively then it might lead to low usage of e-learning platforms by the teachers and students (Almaiah & Almulhem, 2018). On the other hand, if the course is designed effectively then it will lead

to higher acceptance of e-learning system by the students and their performance also increases (Mtebe & Raisamo, 2014). Hence, to prepare these courses for online learning, many instructors who are teaching blended courses for the first time are likely to require a complete overhaul of their courses (Bersin, 2004).

The course's technological design is highly persuading the students' learning and Performance through their course expectations (Liaw, 2008; Lin et al., 2008). Active course design indicates the students' effective outcomes compared to the traditional design (Black & Kassaye, 2014). Learning style is essential for effective course design (Wooldridge, 1995). While creating an online course design, it is essential to keep in mind that we generate an experience for students with different learning styles. Similarly, (Jenkins, 2015) highlighted that the course design attributes could be developed and employed to enhance student success. Hence the hypothesis that the course design significantly affects students' Performance was included in this study.

H2: Course design positively affects the Performance of students.

INSTRUCTOR'S PROMPT FEEDBACK

The factor that improves the student's satisfaction level is prompt feedback (Kinicki et al., 2004). Feedback is defined as information given by lecturers and tutors about the performance of students. Within this context, feedback is a "consequence of performance" (Hattie & Timperley, 2007, p. 81). In education, "prompt feedback can be described as knowing what you know and what you do not related to learning" (Simsek et al., 2017, p.334).

Christensen (2014) studied linking feedback to performance and introduced the positivity ratio concept, which is a mechanism that plays an important role in finding out the performance through feedback. It has been found that prompt feedback helps in developing a strong linkage between faculty and students which ultimately leads to better learning outcomes (Simsek et al., 2017; Chang, 2011).

The emphasis in this study is to understand the influence of prompt feedback on Performance. Feedback gives the information about the students' effective performance (Chang, 2011; Grebennikov & Shah, 2013; Simsek et al., 2017). Prompt feedback enhances student learning experience (Brownlee et al., 2009).

Prompt feedback is the self-evaluation tool for the students (Rogers, 1992) by which they can improve their performance. Eraut (2006) highlighted the impact of feedback on future practice and student learning development. Good feedback practice is beneficial for student learning and teachers to improve students' learning experience (Yorke, 2003). Hence the hypothesis that prompt feedback significantly affects Performance was included in this study.

H3: Prompt feedback of the students positively affects the Performance.

STUDENT'S EXPECTATIONS

Students' expectation. Appleton-Knapp and Krentler (2006) measured the impact of student's expectations on their performance. They pinpointed that the student expectation is important. When the expectations of the students are achieved then it led to the higher satisfaction level of the student (Bates & Kaye, 2014). Student satisfaction is defined as students' ability to compare the desired benefit with the observed effect of a particular product or service (Budur et al., 2019). Students' whose grade expectation is high will show high satisfaction instead of those facing lower grade expectations.

Expectation is a crucial factor that directly influences the Performance of the student. Expectation Disconfirmation Theory (EDT) (Oliver, 1980) was utilized to determine the level of Performance based on their expectations (Schwarz & Zhu, 2015). Student's expectation is the best way to improve their Performance (Brown et al., 2014). It is possible to recognize student expectations to progress Performance level (Gopal, R., Singh, V., & Aggarwal, A.,2021). Finally, the positive approach used in many online learning classes has been shown to place a high expectation on learners (Gold, 2011) and has led to successful outcomes. Hence the hypothesis that expectations of the student significantly affect the Performance was included in this study.

H4: Expectations of the students positively affects the Performance.

METHODOLOGY

The research design is a framework or a model to carry out the research projects. It describes the necessary process for obtaining the useful data and information used to build or solve research questions. Simply, it is the overview plan indicates how you design your research. Research problems are built or solved through the collection of meaningful data and information. In simplest terms, it's a visual representation of your whole research strategy, the most appropriate research method for this study kind is quantitative research, which is what we've used in this study (Saldaña, J.,2021). Associating separate variables with numerical data allows the quantitative approach to encompass a system of inquiry that can be generalized to the population (Finnerty et al., 2013). Data may be acquired quickly and efficiently, and results can be directly related to a study's topic of study through quantitative research (Creswell, 2017). A quantitative outcome is also dependent on the author's competence and arguments to support the hypothesis and findings. Simple empirical relationships are used frequently to gain more knowledge. As a result, this form of study relies heavily on the foundation and impression concept to arrive at correct aspects like hypotheses or worries (Creswell, 2017). Based on the statistics of Halabja University Presidency (2022), the number of students at Halabja University is estimated at 3,500 (Halabja University Presidency, 2022). A simple random sampling

technique was used in this study, to allow generalizing of the study population (Bryman & Bell, 2015). Research conducted by Creswell (2017) recommends a randomized sampling technique, where individual entities within the population size may be selected on equal grounds. The emphasis in selecting a simple randomized sampling is to enable the representation of the sample characteristics closer to the characteristics of the entire population (Sekaran & Bougies, 2016).

Table 1: Measuring items for all variables

Variables	Items	Sources
Quality of Instructor	The instructor communicated effectively	Luekens et al., 2004; Grammatikopoulos et al., 2014
	The instructor was enthusiastic about online teaching	
	The instructor was concerned about student learning	
	The instructor was generally respectful of student learning	
	The instructor was accessible to me outside of the online	
	The instructor used Webinar to create a comfortable learning space	
Course Design	The instructor personalized interactions with me whenever necessary	Wright, 2003; Almaiah & Alyoussef, 2019; Mtebe Raisamo, 2014
	The course was well organized	
	The course was designed to allow assignments to be completed across different learning environments	
	The instructor facilitated the course effectively	
	Web was used to create an efficient learning environment	
Instructor's Prompt Feedback	The course was designed to allow me to take responsibility for my own learning	Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Kinicki et al., 2004
	The instructor responded promptly to my questions about the use of Webinar	
	The instructor responded promptly to my questions about general course requirements	
	The instructor responded promptly to my questions about course assignments	
Student's Expectations	The instructor motivated me to do my best	Knapp & Krentler, 2006; Bates & Kaye, 2014
	The instructor provided models that clearly communicated expectations for weekly group assignments	
	The instructor used good examples to explain statistical concepts	
	The assignments for this course were of appropriate difficulty level	
	The instructor used Webinar design instructional materials that were understandable	
Perceived Performance	Our lecturers are extremely good at explaining things to us	Rono, 2013; Farooq et al., 2011
	The online classes has sharpened my analytic skills	
	An online class really tries to get the best out of all its students	
	This course has helped me develop the ability to plan my own work	
	Online classes has encouraged me to develop my own academic interests as far as possible	
	Online classes has improved my written communication skills	
As a result of doing online classes, one feel more confident about tackling unfamiliar problems		

RESULT AND FINDINGS

The demographic profiles of the respondents including gender, age, academic term, field of study, and expected final are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage of demographic information

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	245	70.0
	Female	105	30.0
	Total	350	100.0
Age	18-22	178	50.9
	23-27	116	33.1
	More than 28	56	16.0
	Total	350	100.0
Academic Term	1 st	49	14.0
	2 nd	109	31.1
	3 rd	114	32.6
	4 th	44	12.6
	5 th	34	9.7
	Total	350	100.0
Field of Study	Medicine	42	12.0
	Dentistry	59	16.9
	Economy	92	26.3
	Pharmacology	44	12.6
	Chemistry	41	11.7
	Faculty of Education	72	20.6
	Total	350	100.0
Expected Final Grades	50 - 60	15	4.3
	61 - 70	34	9.7
	71 - 80	111	31.7
	81 - 90	51	14.6
	More than 90	139	39.7
	Total	350	100.0

Starting from gender, it is evident from the table 2 that in university, majority of the respondents (70%) were male, while the remaining (30%) were female. Moving on to age, majority of the respondents (50.9%) were in the age group of 18-22 years of age, while the least of them were in the more than 28 years old category at (16%). As for the academic term of the respondents in university, most respondents (32.6%) were 3rd years in than study, while the least (9.7%) were 5th years in than study. Based on their Field of Study in university, the respondents mostly (26.3%) were them field in economy, while the least of them (11.7%) were them field in Chemistry. Based on their expected final grades of the respondents mostly (39.7%) were in more than 90, while the least of them were in the 50 - 60 (4.3%).

Table 3: The stability of the instrument Cronbach's alpha for the variables

No.	Variables	No. of items	Cronbach's alpha	Remarks
1	Quality of instructor	7	0.873	Good
2	Course design	5	0.864	Good
3	Prompt feedback of students	4	0.832	Good
4	Students' expectations	5	0.796	Acceptable
5	Students' performance	6	0.832	Good
Total		27	0.952	Excellence

In Table 3, the reliability analysis of the variables from the university data is presented. From the table, it is evident that the Cronbach's alpha coefficient obtained for Students' performance (dependent variable). As for the independent variables, the Cronbach's alpha coefficients obtained are as follows; 0.873 for Quality of instructor, 0.864 for Course design, 0.832 for Prompt feedback of students, and lastly 0.796 for Students' expectations. All the results obtained of the Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the dependent variable as well as for the independent variables ranged from acceptable to good. On the whole, all the measures obtained high Cronbach's alpha reliabilities that ranged from 0.96 -0.873 in the Halabja University-Iraq case, all surpassed the cut-off value of 0.70 recommended by prior studies (Wells & Wollack, 2003). Considering the above acceptable values, all the items were retained, particularly because the students' performance values were 0.832 in Halabja University-Iraq respectively.

Table 4: Pearson's Correlation Analysis of Variables

Variables	quality of instructor	course design	prompt feedback of students	students expectations	students performance
quality of instructor	1				
course design	.685**	1			
prompt feedback of students	.708**	.536**	1		
students expectations	.705**	.659**	.806**	1	
students performance	.691**	.687**	.713**	.807**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

This study employed the rule of thumb establishing that R-value of 0.10, 0.13 and 0.50 indicate low, medium, and strong relationship as recommended by Green et al. (1997). Based on this rule of thumb, in the Halabja University, all the correlation coefficients in the table are positive and significant. In particular, quality of instructor, course design, prompt feedback of students, and students' expectations (independent variables) all registered positive and significant relationships with students' performance (dependent variable). The findings shows that the independent variables all positively correlated at the level of 0.01,

with the highest correlation obtained between students' performance and students' expectations ($r=0.807$, $p<0.01$), and the lowest between prompt feedback of students and course design ($r=0.536$, $p<0.01$). With regards to the relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variable, the results showed the following: quality of instructor correlated with students' performance at ($r=0.691$), course design correlated with students performance at ($r=0.687$), while prompt feedback of students and students performance correlated at ($r=0.713$). In addition, students' expectations correlated with students performance at ($r=0.807$). In sum, all the variables positively correlated with each other in Halabja University.

Table 5: The results of the application of the regression quality of instructor, course design, prompt feedback of students, and students' expectations direct positively correlates with the student's performance

Variables	B	T	Sig.	R	R ²	F	Sig.
quality of instructor	.263	2.168	.031	.841 ^a	.708	209.219	.000 ^b
course design	.100	5.420	.000				
prompt feedback of students	.225	2.515	.012				
students' expectations	.126	8.510	.000				
a. Dependent Variable: student's performance							

Based on the results indicated in the table 5, in the Halabja University, there is a statistical direct significant relationship between quality of instructor, course design, prompt feedback of students, and students' expectations and student's performance at the significance level of ($p =0.05$). The results indicate the correlation coefficient (R) to be 0.841, the (R²) to be 0.708, and the value test (F) to be 209.219. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted.

RECOMMENDATION FOR FUTURE WORK

In view of the above limitations, further empirical research is necessary to expand the scope of the study. It is possible to add to and build upon the existing research framework to improve results and overcome limitations. Future research could also include the views of educators and policy makers to further generalize the findings. The current research is limited to Halabja University only. Therefore, it can be implemented to check the performance of students in other universities. The study is for Iraqi students only; Thus, if the data is collected from different countries, it can give better comparative results to understand the student's perspective.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the aim of the study is to identify the factors that influence students' pictorial performance in relation to online classes during the pandemic period of COVID-19 and to establish the relationship between these variables. The study is of a quantitative nature, and the data was collected from students of Halabja University in Iraq through an online survey who were studying several disciplines (Bachelor's or Master's) a. The SPSS program was used to analyze the proposed hypotheses. The results showed that four independent factors were used in the study. Teacher quality, course design, quick feedback, and student expectations positively influence perceived performance and increase performance, which positively impacts student performance. For educational administration, these four factors are essential for a high level of performance of online educational courses.

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